

1 **Title page**

2 A method for the detection and characterization of technology fronts: analysis of the
3 dynamics of technological change in 3D printing technology.

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9 **Abstract**

10 This paper presents a method for the identification of the “technology fronts” - core
11 technological solutions - underlying a certain broad technology, and the characterization of
12 their change dynamics. We propose an approach based on the Latent Dirichlet Allocation
13 (LDA) model combined with patent data analysis and text mining techniques for the
14 identification and dynamic characterization of the main fronts where actual technological
15 solutions are put into practice. 3D printing technology has been selected to put our method
16 into practice for its market emergence and multidisciplinary. The results show two highly
17 relevant and specialized fronts strongly related with mechanical design that evolve
18 gradually, in our opinion acting as enabling technologies. On the other side, we detected
19 three fronts undergoing significant changes, namely layer-by-layer multimaterial
20 manufacturing, data processing and stereolithography techniques. Laser and electron-beam
21 based technologies take shape in the latter years and show signs of becoming enabling
22 technologies in the future. The technology fronts and data revealed by our method have
23 been convincing to experts and coincident with many technology trends already pointed out
24 in technical reports and scientific literature.

25 **Introduction**

26 Decision making in science and technology (S&T) is an uncertainty-plagued process that
27 combines the expertise and information internally available at the firm with the thorough
28 analysis of external variables that exert influence on the rate/direction of the evolution of
29 technology. The set of techniques and information sources that are put into practice with
30 this purpose, among others, form a well-developed academic and managerial discipline
31 called Future-oriented Technology Analysis (FTA) [1], which spans several activities such as
32 technology foresight, forecasting and technology roadmapping [2], all of which share the
33 purpose of optimizing decision making in S&T. Most of FTA combines eclectic quantitative
34 and qualitative information sources, patent data usually being a frequent choice among the
35 latter. This paper presents a method for the identification of the “technology fronts”
36 underlying a certain technology, and the characterization of their change dynamics. We
37 propose an approach based on the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model combined with
38 patent data analysis and text mining techniques for the identification and dynamic
39 characterization of the main fronts where actual technological solutions are put into
40 practice.

41 What we understand by “technology front” could be described as follows: “core
42 technological solutions underlying certain device or broad development”. The improvement
43 of complex devices over time is often shaped by the incorporation/adaptation of new
44 elements on the device: for example, a new material is used, key features of design are
45 changed, new sensors are embedded and new control systems are put into practice. A good

46 case can be found in the automotive industry: the incorporation of more than 4km of
47 electric wire brought entirely new features to cars and increased their efficiency by
48 gradually substituting previous mechanical/hydraulic solutions, and wireless data
49 transmission might shape the next generation of devices to solve certain shortcomings of
50 current automotive electric wiring-based systems [3]. In this work we aim to detect and
51 characterize the main fronts of technological change that characterize the evolution of a
52 machine type that itself contains many devices that are evolving themselves. What really
53 makes a technological innovation unique, thus patentable, have to be clearly stated in the
54 patent claims: “patents claims are the heart of a patent (...) the claims demarcate in words
55 the boundary of invention (...) only the technology covered in the claims is protected” [4].
56 For patents protecting a new 3D printer design, or any subset of components (such as a
57 particular feeder-heater-nozzle design), the claims should state the points where technology
58 has really changed with respect to prior art, and this is the textual field we propose to
59 analyze in this work to detect and characterize the “technology fronts” underlying evolution
60 in 3D printing technology.

61 3D printing technology is experiencing an explosion in the number of patents filed since
62 2013, according to the data retrieved using the query described in the “data download”
63 section. The number of simple patent families filed that year more than quadrupled the
64 number of patents filed in 2012, and the average growth rate in the number of patents filed
65 each year from 2013 to 2016 stands at a remarkable 75%, as shown by Fig 1. Several authors
66 [5,6] suggest that increasing sales, industry’s growing adoption and a boost in popularity
67 have qualified 3D printing technology as “emergent”, notwithstanding, the first functional
68 solutions in 3D printing date back 30 years.

69

70 **Fig 1. Evolution in the annual number of 3D printing technology patents (simple families)**
71 **filed since year 2004.** Screenshot of the number of patents filed each year since year 2004,
72 retrieved by running the query presented in the “data download” section on the Patseer
73 database (query run on 19 November 2018). The years on the x-axis correspond to the
74 earliest priority year of the simple patent family. It should be noted that data corresponding
75 to year 2017 might present a substantial amount of upside variation due to database
76 updates.

77

78 Many authors trace the end of such “sleeping beauty” behavior back to the expiration of a
79 set of patents protecting key 3D printing technologies, the development of certain enabling
80 technologies and the high expectations on the possibilities of mass customization [7–10].
81 The corporate strategy of patent holders and the limitations of the early machines in terms
82 of affordability, materials and printing quality are among other factors that could explain
83 this phenomenon. The current position of 3D printing technology in the classic technology

84 life cycle stages of emergence (or “introduction”), growth, maturity and saturation depends
85 on the approach chosen in order to define the boundaries of each phase in patent filing
86 analyses. According to Haupt [11], a strongly increasing number of annual patent filings
87 characterizes the “growth” stage, a situation where technology and market uncertainties
88 have disappeared and incremental innovations take the lead in the evolution of the
89 technology: The “emergence” stage is characterized by a slowly growing upward trend, and
90 according to our data 3D printing would have gone beyond this stage in year 2013. At this
91 point it should be noted that an increase in patents typically precedes the introduction of a
92 new technology in the market [12], so 3D printing technology can be considered an
93 emerging technology when analyzing other indicators such as product sales or adoption by
94 industry. Other authors consider that the emergence stage is characterized by a substantial
95 increase in patent activity after a period characterized by a stable number of yearly patents
96 [13,14], using this approach, 3D printing technology could be considered an emerging
97 technology that has just started its growth phase.

98 However, the influence of patent expiration on new developments in 3D printing [6–9] may
99 reoccur in the coming years, due to the recent expiration of certain patents on basic
100 technologies in this field [15]. This would confirm our hypothesis that this technology is at
101 the beginning of a growth phase, possibly pointing at a rise in scientific, public and
102 entrepreneurial attention to 3D printing technology for the years to come. This combination
103 of emergence and multidisciplinary makes 3D printing a fairly heterogeneous field where
104 many techniques and applications evolve at different paces, yet sharing the same broad
105 technological concept, i.e., building an object by adding the material(s) that form that object
106 on a layer-by-layer basis, thus forming a common technological principle. These are a few of
107 the facts that led us to choose 3D printing to put our method into practice.

108 Another reason for choosing this field to conduct our study is the following: 3D printers are
109 devices formed by a wide array of mechanical and electronic components that aim at
110 solving technological challenges such as the processing of information for 3D layer-by-layer
111 manufacturing, the multimaterial processing capabilities, rheology problems, high precision
112 positioning technologies, adherence between layers, etc., thus being fertile in “technology
113 fronts” to be detected, that is to say, key points where technology improvements are taking
114 place, as explained in the paragraphs above. Last but not least, our research team is linked
115 with firms and maker communities in 3D printing that deliver the necessary expert
116 assessment for technology-specific analyses.

117

118 **3D printing technology**

119 The disruption that 3D printing technology is expected to bring is bound to transform
120 business models from the dependence of economies of scale and the massive outsourcing
121 of production facilities to a less wasteful, logistically far more efficient approach, based on

122 mass customization and the re-location of manufacturing centers near the main markets
123 where sales actually take place, thus giving a new boost to the principles of Just in Time
124 production of goods. In addition to this, the manufacturing of complex geometries would be
125 cost-efficient almost regardless of the manufacturing batch size, and materials wasted
126 would be negligible when compared to traditional subtractive manufacturing methods. A
127 special socio-economical challenge posed by the arrival of this technology will be the
128 destabilizing effect of the deep transformation - or sheer reduction - that traditional
129 manufacturing labor force will have to endure under this new paradigm [16,17]. Some
130 authors even draw parallels between the irruption of the mp3 file format and the diffusion
131 of Internet and the widespread adoption of 3D printing technology, suggesting that the days
132 of patent and other copyright protection systems may be numbered [18].

133 In this section we will provide an overview of the main technologies that currently form the
134 state-of-art in 3D printing, using the standard terminology for additive manufacturing
135 technologies defined by committees ISO/TC 261 and F42 from ISO and ASTM, respectively,
136 and published under the standard ISO/ASTM 52900:2015 [19]. This overview aims at giving a
137 bird eye's view of the techniques forming the 3D printing field, more technical details about
138 the techniques described here can be found in the excellent review written by Ngo et al.
139 [20].

140 **VAT Photopolymerization**

141 Photopolymers are a particular type of liquid polymers that polymerize (we could say
142 solidify or harden, for 3D printing purposes) when exposed to visible or ultraviolet (UV)
143 wavelengths. The most frequent commercial materials used in this technology are acrylates,
144 epoxies and vinyl ethers, and well-known applications of photopolymerization include the
145 plastic coating of paper or cardboard and tooth fillings using dental composite. The first
146 patent of a 3D printing machine based on VAT photopolymerization, titled "Apparatus for
147 production of three-dimensional objects by stereolithography" was filed in 1984 by Charles
148 Hull, hence the popularity of the name "stereolithography" to refer to this technology [21].
149 The typical design of a 3D printing machine based on this technology is formed by a platform
150 that controls the Z axis and a light source that can be directed to solidify the polymer in the
151 desired points on a layer-by-layer basis. The platform will move downwards as the printing
152 progresses, and once the product is finished the remaining polymer liquid in the vat is
153 evacuated. The original sketch (Fig 2) presented in the patent filed by Charles Hull is a good
154 example of the basic design of such devices.

155

156 **Fig 2. Sketch corresponding to the first VAT photopolymerization machine.** Original sketch
157 of the "apparatus for production of three-dimensional objects by stereolithography",
158 extracted from the US patent US4575330A.

159 Additional features of these devices often include a passing blade system to improve the
160 union between layers. In some cases an extra curing of the finished product is necessary for
161 it to achieve the desired mechanical properties [22]. This is one of the 3D printing methods
162 where the highest printing resolution can be achieved and a very promising technology for
163 the field of bioengineering, where fully customized implants can be built in an efficient
164 manner [23] as well as medical templates and biomodels for surgery preparation [24,25].

165 **Material Jetting**

166 This technology follows a process similar to the conventional ink jet printers, in fact, it is
167 frequently found in the literature under the heading of “inkjet printing”. Liquid materials
168 with a varying degree of viscosity are deposited on a platform where they are hardened,
169 either by drying, cooling or chemical reaction (this is the case of concrete 3D printers, for
170 example [26]) or by curing with UV light. Most current industrial material jetting printers
171 use piezoelectric drop-on-demand (DOD) systems, instead of continuous flow systems [27].
172 Material jetting is the main technique for 3D printing using ceramic materials in solution or
173 colloidal form [20], the fabrication of geometrically complex bone-implants using
174 compatible biomaterials is one of the applications gaining traction in this technology [28,29]

175 **Binder Jetting**

176 This technology is often named three-dimensional printing or 3DP, and works by jetting a
177 binding material on a certain area of a layer of powdered material, thus gluing together the
178 base material and forming a compact layer. The machine then deposits a new layer of
179 powdered material and the printing head deposits the adhesive material on the points
180 corresponding to the next layer, these steps follow each other until the product is finished.
181 Binder jetting devices usually have a mobile base platform (see Fig 3) in charge of
182 determining the Z- axis position of the layer being printed. This method permits a greater
183 range of materials, including polymers, ceramics and metals, and is also suitable for
184 fabricating multi-material products that combine different materials on each layer, however,
185 these advantages are offset by the fact that it often produces poorer precision and surface
186 finishes than material jetting, and the resulting product is more porous, which decreases its
187 mechanical properties. The fragility of the printed parts can be reduced by further finishing
188 operations such as infiltration [30].

189

190 **Fig 3. Binder jetting system.** This figure represents the binder jetting system method, where
191 a binder is deposited on a powdered material to create compact layers that give shape to
192 the finished product. Source: [30]

193 Binder jetting is the most successful 3D printing technique in the pharmaceutical industry,
194 making it possible to customize key variables in drugs, such as release-characteristics,
195 dosages and drug combinations, among others [31,32]. Operation at room temperature also

196 makes this technique very suitable for building complete biostructures that embed both
197 biological agents and living cells [33].

198 **Material Extrusion**

199 This process shares some technical similarities with the material jetting technique but with
200 the key difference of operating through a heated nozzle that merges and extrudes a
201 material that is typically fed in a filament (solid) format, as shown in Fig 4. This technique is
202 also known by the names “fused deposition modeling” (FDM) or “fused filament fabrication”
203 (FFF) and was first patented by Scott Crump in 1989 (US Grant US5340433A) and
204 commercialized by the firm Stratasys.

205

206 **Fig 4. FFF printing system.** Diagram showing the basis of the FFF technique. Source: [34]

207 This is the most widespread and inexpensive (at least at basic level) process for 3D printing,
208 and after the main patents that protected the technology expired, a vibrant open-design
209 community has been grouped in the RepRap project, an initiative aimed at creating an
210 affordable desktop manufacturing system that would enable the individual to self-
211 manufacture a wide range of devices [35]. At a basic level this technique is inexpensive, but
212 the accuracy and density of the manufactured products are usually below the levels that can
213 be achieved with other 3D printing processes, even though the competitiveness of FDM is
214 improving rapidly [36]. The thermoplastics Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) and
215 Polylactide Acid (PLA) are the most common materials used in FDM, however, the simplicity
216 and affordability of this technique begs the development of new materials that would
217 expand its application domain beyond the thermoplastics. Several studies have been
218 published on the mechanical properties of ABS composites using both metallic and non-
219 metallic elements, typically reporting poorer mechanical properties but improved thermal
220 conductivity, dielectric permittivity and radiation shielding features in some metal-ABS
221 composites [37,38]. The possibility of manufacturing sintered ceramic and metallic parts has
222 also been studied; in this case the feedstock for the FDM process is usually formed by
223 powdered ceramic/metallic material bound together in an organic matrix. After the part is
224 printed, the organic binder is removed and sintering and/or infiltration treatments are used
225 to finish the part [39]. The use of biomaterials in FDM printing techniques is mainly aimed at
226 building biological scaffolds, commonly using polycaprolactone (PCL) and bioactive glass
227 composites to build a structure that acts as an interface for facilitating the regeneration of
228 cellular tissues. The majority of applications rule out directly incorporating living cells or
229 biological agents to the printing material due to the high temperatures during the extrusion
230 process [33].

231 **Powder Bed Fusion**

232 Several techniques that share common elements are grouped under this category: All
233 powder bed fusion processes work on a powdered layer of the feedstock that will be

234 selectively melted or sintered, on a layer-by-layer basis, until the finished product is formed,
235 and blades or rollers (see Fig 5) are generally used for distributing the powder once the
236 previous layer has been finished. Gibson [40] distinguishes between the laser-based and the
237 electron beam-based techniques: Electron beam based techniques can only be used with
238 metals, since the processed material must be conductive, while laser based techniques, in
239 addition to metals, can also be used with ceramics and polymers. Electron beam techniques
240 offer a more energy-efficient process but trail laser techniques in resolution and surface
241 finishing quality.

242

243 **Fig 5. Selective laser sintering process.** Schematic representation of the selective laser
244 sintering process. Source: Materialgeez /Wikimedia commons

245 Laser techniques are often divided into selective laser sintering (SLS) and selective laser
246 melting (SLM) techniques, depending on the degree of melting achieved on the powder
247 particles. Most commercial processes can be classified as “liquid phase sintering – partial
248 melting” (corresponding to the most typical SLS methods) and “full melting” (corresponding
249 to SLM) categories, but depending on the binding mechanism “solid state sintering” and
250 “chemically induced binding” can also be defined [41]. Powder bed fusion techniques have
251 been successfully used to produce metallic components with mechanical properties
252 comparable to those manufactured by traditional means, however, steep temperature
253 gradients and high cooling rates in the printing process can substantially alter the properties
254 of the printed product [42]. The processing of biomaterials using SLS techniques has also
255 produced highly satisfactory results, particularly in applications requiring high product
256 resolution [43]. The range of metallic and ceramic materials that can be used as a feedstock
257 for powder bed fusion techniques is highly dependent on the melting point, particularly in
258 SLM techniques, which are based on the complete fusion of the materials being processed
259 [20].

260 **Sheet Lamination**

261

262 Sheet lamination differs from the rest of additive manufacturing techniques explained in this
263 section in the fact that the feedstock is provided to the process in the shape of fully finished
264 sheets that must be joined together. The most basic technology for sheet lamination is the
265 laminated object manufacturing (LOM) technique, which directly uses adhesive materials or
266 simple mechanical means to join the material sheets together. This technique includes
267 several sub-classifications, depending on whether the material layers are feed to the
268 process in their final shape or not (“bond then form” vs “form then bond”) [44]. Ultrasonic
269 additive manufacturing (UAM) is used for metallic material sheet lamination, and is based
270 on the sequential bonding of metal foils using ultrasonic metal welding, often requiring
271 further mechanical processing of the welded foils by CNC milling [20]. Ultrasonic

272 consolidation is also a promising technique for achieving the embedding of composite
273 materials in a metal matrix, avoiding some of the disadvantages of melting and casting
274 metals [45,46].

275 **Directed energy deposition**

276 The directed energy deposition technique uses a laser or electron beam in order to melt a
277 material and shape a part on a layer-by-layer basis. The key difference between this method
278 and the powder bed fusion method lies in the fact that in this case the material is not pre-
279 laid, but is simultaneously deposited and melted on a surface, thus no powder bed is
280 required. This method can be used with polymers, ceramic and metallic materials as long as
281 it is based on a laser device, given that electron beam based devices can only work with
282 conductive materials. The feedstock can be fed in powdered or wire form, wire is more
283 convenient to store and process, but processing conditions are decisive to achieve the
284 desired quality, with wire tip position, feed-rate and direction, laser spot size and laser
285 power being some of the variables with higher impact on the resulting quality of the
286 process. The applications based on powder are more frequent partly due to greater
287 possibilities for using powdered additive materials [47].

288

289 **Fig 6. Sketch of a multiple nozzle direct energy deposition process.** Schematic
290 representation of a 2-nozzle, powder-based direct energy deposition process. Source: [48]

291 The processing material can be any metal powder that is weldable [49], and the feeding
292 system can be coaxial to the laser or side-fed by using one or several nozzles, as shown in
293 Fig 6. This technique is suitable for producing finished parts, but one of its key advantages
294 lies in the possibility of printing on elements that are already built, thus many directed
295 energy deposition applications are focused on restoration or cladding [20,50]

296 **Barriers and improvement points**

297 Despite already being a “hot topic” in the world of manufacturing technologies, according to
298 a study published by PricewaterhouseCoopers [51] actual real-world implementations of 3D
299 printing technology in manufacturing industries are predominantly (48.8%) located in
300 prototyping and experimental facilities, while 13.2% of surveyed firms use this technology
301 for both prototyping and production purposes and only 9.1% of firms use 3D Printing solely
302 for manufacturing. The areas presented in Table 1 are considered future improvements that
303 should occur in 3D printing in order to seize the multiple opportunities that this technology
304 has to offer [52].

305 **Table 1. Key points to improve in current state-of-art 3D printing [52]**

AREA	KEY POINTS
Performance	Increased printing speed. Increased resolution.

	Possibility for autonomous operation.
Multi-material printing	Incorporation of multiple materials in the same object, including composites combining plastic and metallic materials [8].
Finished products	Ability to print fully functional and active systems that incorporate many modules, such as embedded sensors, electronics, etc.
Ease of use	Suppress sources of error and reliability failures, such as support structure generation, part orientation, auto-calibration.
Software	Ease of use for design & operation Optimization for accuracy Generation of printing files directly from existing objects or 2D images

306 This table explains some of the trends with higher influence on the developments in 3D
307 printing.

308 When non-adopters were asked about 3D printing technology, the most cited reasons for
309 not entering additive manufacturing were the cost of printers (42.1%) and the lack of
310 internal expertise to fully exploit this technology (32.2%), followed by the uncertainty about
311 the quality of printed parts (33,1%) and the slowness of printing process (25.6%). It is worth
312 noting that the limited amount of materials suitable for 3D printing scores in fifth place
313 (22.3%) [51]. The nature of these problems affects many parts and processes in the 3D
314 printer and shows the transversality of the solutions that will be required. While both
315 printers and printing materials are subject to limits based on physics, software
316 improvements are set to introduce transversal developments that could accelerate the path
317 to extensive implementation of 3D printing technology in many applications. Geometrically
318 complex, multi-material product printing is a specific case where software solutions can add
319 the ultimate edge to already available high-precision printing techniques [53], in addition to
320 many successful applications of 3D printing to medical fields, thanks to the development of
321 software solutions able to generate 3D objects directly from data obtained by tomography
322 or magnetic resonance [54].

323 On the new material development side, there are also significant research fronts dealing
324 with the development of new materials for 3D printing, particularly in metals. Metal printing
325 is in many cases restricted to aluminum and brass in desktop printers, due to the high
326 melting points of industrial-grade metals such as high tensile steel. Some authors state that
327 this limitation could be overcome in the future by using nanoscale-sized metal particles,
328 which fuse at dramatically lower temperatures as the particle size becomes smaller than 50
329 nm [52]. Improvements in the optical properties of the powder used (e.g., absorption,
330 reflection and transmittance) are also decisive for achieving this purpose [55].

331 **Technology analysis**

332 Technological knowledge is a vital support for strategy, innovation and operational
333 processes at firms. The analysis of technology is underpinning management of technology

334 both at micro (firms) and macro (R&D policies) levels, the information contained in patents
335 being one of the crucial information inputs of such systems, both due to the wealth of
336 information they contain and the availability of data and methods to extract activable
337 information for pertinent decision making. The analysis of patent portfolios can also give
338 relevant insight into the R&D goals pursued by competitors [56,57].

339 Understanding of the dynamics of technological change and the forecasting of future
340 changes is another interesting output of patent analysis. Benson and Magee [58] proposed a
341 method for estimating the rate of technological progress in a particular domain, using
342 patent data. Those domains with higher a progress rate are deemed - at least temporarily -
343 to dominate the competitive markets except for a few resistant niches, this evidences the
344 potential of quantitative technology analysis for understanding the future of technology
345 [59]. The different stages (emergence, growth, maturity and saturation) of the technology
346 life cycle can also be identified using patent data, as shown by Gao et al. [60].

347 While many relevant S&T questions can be addressed by exploiting the structured data
348 present on patents, there is a vast wealth of information available therein in the form of
349 textual, unstructured information. Text-mining techniques allow the structuration, cleaning
350 and further processing of semi-structured and unstructured textual data in order to make
351 them suitable for feeding “conventional” data-mining procedures that would enable the
352 extraction of relevant knowledge from data [61]. Natural Language Processing (NLP), term
353 consolidation, thesaurization and noise-removal techniques are among the most frequent
354 steps in text mining processes applied to textual information contained in abstracts, titles or
355 claims of patents [62,63]. The review conducted by Abbas et al. [64] is recommended
356 reading for an extensive description of the main types and purposes of text-mining analysis
357 applied to patent data.

358 **METHODOLOGY**

359 **Data download**

360 The first step of this study required the building of a dataset containing the patents related
361 to 3D printing technology. Initially, the approach of downloading the full B33 subclass
362 “additive manufacturing technology” present in the IPC classification scheme was
363 considered, however, a large number of patents simply describing objects that could be 3D
364 printed fall into this category, thus not being descriptive of the 3D printing technological
365 developments we were looking for. A deeper look into the subclass description shows that
366 “this subclass is for obligatory supplementary classification of subject matter already
367 classified as such in other classification places, when the subject matter contains an aspect
368 of additive manufacturing”, thus confirming the presence of undesired records in this
369 approach. The conventional method of building a query was put into practice instead,
370 leading to the following query, adapted to the syntax of Patseer patent database [65]. The

371 time limits were set in accordance with the filing of the first - one may even say
 372 foundational - patents in 3D printing technology [10]:

373 TA:((three w0 dimens* w0 print*) OR (3D print*) OR (additive w0 manuf*)) AND PRD:
 374 ([1985-01-01 TO 2017-12-31])

375 These terms were looked for in patent’s title and abstract fields, retrieving 22034 simple
 376 families of patents (from this point forward we will interchangeably use the term “patents”,
 377 referring to simple families of patents as returned by Patseer database) that were first filed
 378 (priority date) between years 1985 and 2017. This query was run on days 22, 23 and 24 of
 379 February 2018. The distribution of patents across the years was highly uneven; very few
 380 patents in 3D printing were filed in the 80’s and 90’s in contrast with the boom that took
 381 place from 2013 onwards. A review of the earliest patents led us to conclude that
 382 technology development was relatively stagnant during that period and that probably no
 383 significant information is lost by aggregating the patents corresponding to early years. Table
 384 2 shows the time intervals that were set for studying the evolution of technology fronts
 385 across time:

386 **Table 2. Time intervals set for the analysis**

YEARS	NUMBER OF PATENT FAMILIES
2017	2987
2016	6558
2015	5827
2014	3659
2013	1623
2006-12	1000
1985-2005	380

387 This table shows the time intervals set for this study and the number of patent families
 388 corresponding to each interval

389 As previously explained, patents contain vital information items for addressing several
 390 issues concerning technology evolution. The very core of the patent in the event of litigation
 391 or prosecution lies in its claims: these are textual sentences defining critical elements of the
 392 patent and usually the primary subject of examination. It seems reasonable to posit that
 393 patent claims could be the sentences that convey more information about the key aspects
 394 where the proposed technological solution adds value, and an appropriate information field
 395 for identifying the technology fronts underlying 3D printing, by means of text-mining.

396 **Text mining procedure**

397 The dataset built in the previous step contains key information about the technology fronts
 398 underlying 3D printing techniques, but it is necessary to separate the wheat from the chaff
 399 in order to detect the main components or areas in which technological advance has
 400 occurred. Topic modeling is a machine learning technique that deals with the problem of
 401 automatically classifying sets of documents into themes, where each of the documents

402 under study consists of a mixture of topics. In addition to this, each document has a
403 “gamma” value for each topic, that could be interpreted as the proportion of words from
404 each document that are generated from that topic [66], which notably improves the
405 subsequent process of interpretation and labeling of topics [62,67]. Topic modeling has led
406 to satisfactory results in automatic classification of scientific publications [68] and the
407 robustness and limitations of the method for several types of data have also been tested
408 [69]. The R package “topicmodels” was used in this study for fitting a Latent Dirichlet
409 Allocation (LDA) model using the Variational Expectation-Maximization (VEM) algorithm
410 [70].

411 The input for the LDA analysis is a document-term matrix containing the number of times
412 each term occurs in the claims of each patent. Claims are a free text field, so a thorough
413 text-mining cleaning process must be conducted in order to remove pronouns, adjectives
414 and common-use terms such as “invention” that, being predominant in term frequency, are
415 useless for interpreting the topic structure of data. Our text-mining process is described in
416 Fig 7.

417

418 **Fig 7. Text mining process.** Diagram showing the text-mining steps leading to obtaining the
419 document-term matrices. This process is replicated for each time interval.

420 A first step consists in transforming patent claims using a proprietary NLP/Words algorithm
421 in version 10.0 of Vantage Point[®] (VP) text mining software [71] for sentence splitting and
422 part-of-speech (POS) tagging. This step produces a list formed by the relative frequency of
423 words and the POS identification of each word (noun, adjective, adverb, verb), while
424 removing pronouns and other textual noise. However, from a semantic point of view the
425 same word could be present more than once in this list due to word inflections, so the next
426 step consisted in a cleanup in order to merge the inflected forms; this was done using the
427 “list cleanup” command in VP, this process generates a thesaurus that contains the
428 information of the inflected terms that have been merged into a single standard form. This
429 same thesaurus has been used to standardize the terms present in the full text of patent
430 claims. At this point we decided to exclude the verbs from the analysis, since verbs strongly
431 need the presence of the adjacent words for their interpretation - this is the case of
432 “comprise” or “move”, for example - while nouns, adjectives and adverbs, indicating
433 material types, properties or machine parts have a more straightforward interpretation. This
434 bag-of-words (BOW) approach inevitably involves the loss of the information contained in
435 the syntactical structure of text, a loss that can be partially reduced by using higher order n-
436 grams or complementing the BOW by using proximity indicators that capture the
437 information contained in the syntactic order of the words present in text. However, the
438 option of using N-grams in the subsequent steps was discarded because of the sparsity of
439 resulting document-term matrices, which produced meaningless results.

440 The last step of the process consisted of a Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency
441 (TFIDF) analysis, this process weighs a set of terms present in a collection of documents
442 (patent claims, in this case), penalizing the terms that occur in many documents (these have
443 a likelihood of being general terms, with no particular relevance to characterize the
444 contents of a document) and giving advantage to those terms that occur frequently, but are
445 not widespread in the document collection [72,73]. We pragmatically set a minimum TFIDF
446 threshold of 0.03 to discard the “general” terms and took the top 300 terms - according to
447 the number of patents where that word exceeded such a threshold - to build the document-
448 term matrix with which to feed the LDA analysis. This process was replicated for each time
449 interval described in section “data download”.

450 The authors recommend using the R packages “openNLP” [74] and “koRpus” [75] for
451 reproducing the text mining steps that in this study have been conducted using VP
452 proprietary software.

453 **Topic analysis and characterization**

454 The application of the LDA model requires setting the desired number of topics in advance.
455 The output of the LDA showed differences between time intervals, partly due to the
456 different sample size of each interval (see the reference Tang et al. [69]) nonetheless we
457 detected that the more straightforward interpretation of topics was achieved using 7 topics
458 for most of the intervals (see Fig 8). The interpretation of the topics was conducted
459 combining the analysis of the terms and patents that had the higher beta/gamma values
460 (top beta word list for words, gamma higher than 0.5 for patents), on each topic. As
461 explained in “text mining procedure” section, the R package “topicmodels” produces an
462 estimation of the likelihood of words (beta) and documents (gamma) being generated in
463 each topic. Fig 8 describes this process and shows the number of topics that were set for
464 LDA analysis in each time interval.

465

466 **Fig 8. Topic modeling and sub-dataset building process.** Diagram showing the process
467 followed from the document-term matrices obtained by text mining to the building of sub-
468 datasets containing the core information to characterize the technology fronts. The number
469 of topics obtained for each time interval is shown.

470 At this point of the analysis we are interested in characterizing the behavior of the
471 technology fronts detected by using topic modeling. While some technology fronts can be
472 reasonably adjusted to the quandaries of a certain technique in 3D printing (see results
473 section) we expect to find transversal fronts that refer to technical elements that are
474 present in a variable proportion across several patents which may not have these
475 transversal elements as a core contribution. In this paper we propose a data subsetting
476 method based on the gamma coefficients returned by the model, so we can build samples
477 of patents in which claims have the higher probability of focusing on the technical element

478 we wish to characterize. After interpreting the topics in each interval, we built several sub-
479 datasets (one per topic and time interval) consisting of the patents that had a gamma
480 coefficient equal or higher than 0.5 on each topic. According to our method, these datasets
481 condense the patents that more clearly represent the essence of each technology front.
482 Hereafter we will use the expressions “technology front” and “topic” indistinctly.

483 **Technology change characterization**

484 A few topics had ambiguous interpretation and were discarded from this analysis, and seven
485 clearly defined topics were identified that had a remarkable continuity across the analyzed
486 time intervals, thus allowing the analysis of technological change over time. As previously
487 explained in the “topic analysis and characterization” section, we built several databases for
488 each time interval, each of the databases containing the patents that had a gamma factor
489 higher than 0.5 on a given topic. We propose the following set of indicators based on patent
490 data in order to study the evolution of technology fronts over time, the word in brackets is
491 the abbreviation we chose for each indicator:

- 492 - Number of forward citations per patent (FORPAT): It can be stated that a certain
493 correlation exists between the citations a patent receives and its technological
494 impact on a particular field [59,76,77], or even on the economic value of the
495 patent [78].
- 496 - Average age of backward citations (YEARBACK): Domains that cite more
497 immediate patents should have higher rates of technological progress [79], as
498 demonstrated by Magee & Benson [59].
- 499 - Patent international classification codes (IPCPAT, IPCNEW): Patent classification
500 analysis can be used to detect important aspects of technological evolution such
501 as the interdisciplinarity, which could lead to improved technological outcomes
502 [59,77,79,80]. We propose an approach based on the analysis of the amount of
503 unique IPC codes (at group level) per patent present on each technology front
504 (IPCPAT) and the % of new IPC codes emerging for each time interval (IPCNEW).
505 To qualify as “new IPC”, each of the IPC’s is tested against the cumulative IPC’s
506 corresponding to previous years, so technologies with longer trajectories will
507 have a significantly lower IPCNEW value than recently emerged technology
508 fronts. A more accurate perception about the object of study change dynamics is
509 achieved by comparing the technologies at the same point of their trajectories.

510 We complement these indicators with an additional text-mining study of technology
511 changes. With this purpose in mind, we replicated the text-mining steps explained in the
512 “text mining procedure” section on each of the sub-datasets, in order to identify the key
513 terms that returned a TFIDF value higher or equal to 0.03 in at least one patent. In addition
514 to this, the terms that were not present in at least 5% of the patents of the sub-dataset
515 were removed. The terms in this list were arranged according to the number of patents
516 where they got a TFIDF higher or equal to 0.03, in decreasing order, so the most relevant

517 and significant terms were at the top of that list. Comparing these lists across time for each
518 technology front could give us a measure of the rate of technology change therein. This was
519 done by building a vector term were the terms were weighed according to the inverse value
520 of their position in the list described above. This process is outlined in Fig 9.

521

522 **Fig 9. Process for building the term vectors.** The information contained in the sub-datasets
523 built in the previous step is text-mined in order to extract the key concepts therein and term
524 vectors are built for each time interval, which will allow us to conduct a comparative
525 analysis across time.

526 These term vectors were built for each technology front and time interval, thereby allowing
527 us to detect changes in the relevance of technological concepts over time. Terms that
528 change their rank in the term vector from interval T1 to T2 will see their weight ($1/n$)
529 changed. Terms that disappear from interval T1 to T2 (they do not exceed the TFIDF ≥ 0.03
530 and relative 5% presence threshold) get zero weight in the term vector corresponding to T2.
531 This method gives a quantitative proxy of the technology change taking place in each topic
532 by calculating the Euclidean distance between vectors corresponding to consecutive time
533 intervals (TERMVEC). TERMVEC is a proxy to detect changes in the composition and
534 relevance of the top concepts dominating a technological area. Moreover, we add another
535 indicator to measure the % of unprecedented terms (terms occurring for the first time on a
536 technology front) corresponding to each time interval. Only the terms that exceed the TFIDF
537 and relative presence threshold are considered, so these concepts satisfy the dual condition
538 of relevance and novelty (NEWTERM). A persistent and higher than average presence of
539 these new terms is a signal of technology change over time [81]. Given that terms from each
540 time interval are compared with the cumulative amount of terms present in previous
541 intervals, comparisons between technology fronts should be made at the same point of
542 maturity. Technologies generally have a higher chance of having many new terms in their
543 early years of development.

544 It should be noted that the analysis of each technology front using these indicators is
545 performed on a relative basis with respect to the values produced by the rest of the fronts.
546 To be persistently above or below the average value will be the determining factor to
547 analyze the influence of each variable on the rate of change of a given technology front.

548 **RESULTS & DISCUSSION**

549 The first feature concerning technology evolution in the 3D printing field to draw our
550 attention was the evolution in total patent number shown in Table 2. The annual patent
551 filings have been growing at an average rate of 65% from year 2013 to 2016, with this rate
552 dramatically dropping in year 2017: that year added just under half of the patents added the
553 year before. A re-run of our query as of 14 May 2018 (Patseer database is updated weekly

554 with new additions/modifications of contents) confirms this slowdown but moderates the
555 drop, 2017 patent filings fall 37% when compared to 2016 data. According to plain patent
556 production, there is enough evidence to consider that 3D printing may be achieving
557 maturity in some of its main technologies.

558 The LDA model has produced coherent results by setting 7 topics for most of the time
559 intervals analyzed. As explained in the “methodology” section, topic interpretation is
560 considerably eased by the beta/gamma values associated with every word and patent in the
561 dataset, which reflect the probabilities of such words or patents being generated from that
562 topic. Fig 10 shows the 7-topic structure corresponding to data from year 2014. The terms
563 with higher probability (beta) of being generated in each of the topics are listed.

564

565 **Fig 10. Topic structure corresponding to year 2014 data.** 7-topic solution produced by LDA
566 model with data corresponding to year 2014.

567 We found an interesting pattern in data that at the same time enabled us to conduct a
568 technology change analysis: there is a stable set of technology fronts (topics) that can be
569 detected in several consecutive time intervals. Fig 11 shows the full list of identified
570 technology fronts and the time span each of them is present.

571

572 **Fig 11. List of technology fronts.** Labels of the technology fronts detected in the sub-
573 datasets and the time span each technology front is present.

574 The following is a brief description of each front, according to our analysis of the terms and
575 patents with highest beta/gamma on each. The names in brackets are the abbreviations for
576 each front:

- 577 - Printing materials (PRINTMAT): Patents on new materials for 3D printing,
578 including composites and mixtures of elements, with a description of
579 physicochemical properties.
- 580 - Stereolithography (SLA): Devices involving a full array of photo-curing
581 technologies, its raw materials (mainly polymeric resins), apparatus design, light
582 sources and methods for obtaining products using this technology.
- 583 - 3D printing data (3D DATA): Data obtaining, processing and data input for 3D
584 printing purposes. Automatic obtaining of printing data from 3D models or 2D
585 images. Scanning. Data transfer systems.
- 586 - Printing head (PRINTHEAD): Patents heavily related with printing head
587 configurations, temperature, feed and other control-related issues and designs,
588 including multi-nozzle and anti-obstruction designs.
- 589 - Multilayer printing (MULTILAYER): Printing methods involving multi-layer
590 technology, mainly either involving printing with different materials or making

- 591 layers - surface treatments included - on a preexisting, not necessarily 3D printed
592 material.
- 593 - Mechanic transmission & positioning (T&P): Patents dealing with precision
594 positioning of parts/printing head, step-by-step motor elements and the
595 mechanic transmissions used in 3D printing technology.
 - 596 - Laser/electron beam melting & sintering (LASERBEAM): Both melting and
597 sintering-based 3D printers (and the parts thereof) aimed at metal/composite
598 material printing. Both laser and electron beam based devices are present.
 - 599 - Powdered materials: A topic present only in 1985-2005 year interval, mainly
600 dealing with powder-based 3D printing techniques with a noticeable presence of
601 medicine-release systems.
 - 602 - Electronic control systems: User-machine interaction devices and systems for
603 automatic control of various aspects of 3D printing machines or networks formed
604 by them. Topic present only in year 2017.

605 Experts confirm the coherency of the technology front structure present in our data,
606 corroborating that topic modeling has unveiled both main technologies behind 3D printing
607 and critical elements of these devices that strongly influence the success of developments in
608 this industry. As explained in the “methodology” section, our next step consisted in building
609 sub-databases for each topic, containing the set of patents that had a gamma higher or
610 equal to 0.5. This data subsetting allowed us to conduct a highly-focused technology change
611 analysis on each topic. Technology fronts “Powdered materials” and “Electronic control
612 systems” were excluded from this part of the analysis due to lack of observations, so
613 subsequent steps of the study refer to the remaining 7 fronts that show certain continuity.
614 Another fact that should be noted is the absence of the SLA front in some of the time
615 intervals. After considering its removal, we opted for including it in the technology analysis
616 for the following reasons: First, the topic is very straightforwardly interpreted; our data
617 clearly shows that this is a neatly defined technology front in 3D printing. Second, we think
618 that it is advisable to leave room for a certain amount of variability when using
619 dimensionality-reduction or other heuristic techniques on time series: temporal gaps should
620 be allowed and the focus should instead be placed on the broader picture.

621 The analysis of the forward citations per patent on each dataset (FORPAT) shows a
622 downward trend across the entire interval analyzed, for all the technologies: this was
623 something to be expected since recent patents tend to have fewer citations than older ones.
624 In order to ease the comparisons between technology fronts we normalized each front’s
625 FORPAT dividing it by the average FORPAT for each time interval. Data points above one
626 (red dashed line) show receiving higher than average citation during that period (Fig 12),
627 there were no citations received for any of the fronts in year 2017.

628

629 **Fig 12. FORPAT for each technology front.** Evolution of the FORPAT indicator for each
630 technology front, normalized. Points above the red dashed line indicate higher than average
631 forward citations.

632 The T&P front clearly stands out as the technology front with a higher number of citations
633 per patent for the entire time interval where this front is present. As discussed before, this
634 indicator is considered as a proxy for technological impact. In our context, this could mean
635 that transversal developments in precision mechanical elements are of key importance for
636 the development of 3D printing technology. This is a technological feature directly related to
637 the resolution of the printed object, and a key enabling technology (among others) when
638 printing complex geometries. Furthermore, PRINTHEAD is also cited above average, and it is
639 related with technical features similar to those of the T&P front, particularly considering the
640 maximum printing resolution achievable with the device. According to our data, these two
641 trends would indicate an evolution of technology closely pursuing higher resolution printing
642 techniques, perhaps to the detriment of other improvement areas. The spike in relative
643 citations for LASERBEAM front is also remarkable, a sign that should be further studied as
644 more data become available. On the other side, MULTILAYER front consistently performs
645 below average, pointing at a decrease in the technological impact of layer-by-layer based
646 multimaterial printing technologies, including surface treatments based on 3D technology.

647 An analysis of the average age of the citations made by the patents on each technology
648 front (YEARBACK) is shown in Fig 13, the bars show the average age of citations made in
649 each time period. Values below these bars indicate that the technology front is citing more
650 recent patents than the average corresponding to that time interval.

651

652 **Fig. 13. YEARBACK for each technology front.** This figure shows the evolution of YEARBACK
653 indicator for each technology front. Data points above the bars indicate older than average
654 backward citations.

655 When patents corresponding to a field tend to cite more recently developed technologies, it
656 is usually interpreted as a sign of increased rate of technology change. T&P technology front
657 cites more recent developments across all the time intervals analyzed, thus complementing
658 the “high relevance” signal returned by this front with FORPAT with an “increased rate of
659 change” indicator, as shown by YEARBACK. 3D DATA, as to be expected from a strongly
660 software-based technology front, remains below average with the exception of a spike in
661 year 2017. On the contrary, MULTILAYER and SLA show relatively old citations when
662 compared to the rest of fronts, pointing at the possibility of stagnation of these fields. Both
663 LASERBEAM and PRINTMAT show a persistent “modernization” of their citation patterns,
664 further research could reveal if this correlation is due to the development of new
665 metal/ceramic materials for laser/electron beam 3D printing.

666 The interdisciplinarity of a technology front is also an interesting factor to analyze, since the
667 biggest opportunities for innovation often emerge from the interaction of different technical
668 fields. Here we base our analysis on two indicators, the number of unique IPC codes per
669 patent (IPCPAT) on one side, and the % of new IPC codes (IPC codes not present before,
670 IPCNEW) that are unique to each time interval on the other. Figs 14 and 15 respectively
671 show the values of these indicators over time, the bars indicate the average value of each
672 indicator for each interval.

673

674 **Fig 14. IPCPAT for each technology front.** This figure shows the evolution of IPCPAT
675 indicator for each technology front. Data points above the bars indicate higher than average
676 IPC's per patent rates.

677 The technological diversity indicator IPCPAT behaves as expected: the predominantly
678 mechanical technology fronts (PRINTHEAD, T&P) are well below the average while
679 MULTILAYER and PRINTMAT are above, probably due to the variety of materials and
680 techniques that these technology fronts involve, which increase the total number of unique
681 IPCs present in the technology front. LASERBEAM is also above average across all the
682 intervals, indicating a variety of technologies and materials forming part of this front.
683 Despite being on the average of the rest of technologies, the interdisciplinarity in SLA shows
684 a spike in year 2017 that will be corroborated by other variables detailed further on in this
685 study.

686 As explained before, it is logical to find a decreasing trend on the IPCNEW indicator in all
687 technologies, given the increased difficulty over time for an IPC to qualify as "new".
688 However, some interesting conclusions can be drawn from Fig 15:

689

690 **Fig 15. IPCNEW for each technology front.** This figure shows the evolution of IPCNEW
691 indicator for each technology front. Data points above the bars indicate higher than average
692 incorporation of new IPC's to the technology front.

693 While IPCPAT gives information about the interdisciplinarity of a given technology, IPCNEW
694 informs about the level of novelty of the diversification taking place in that technology. This
695 helps us to put the increase in multidisciplinary of LASERBEAM and PRINTMAT into
696 context: Multidisciplinary is increasing, but it does so mainly by spreading the technology
697 fields (IPC) that were already present in these fronts. According to our data, MULTILAYER is
698 above the average in both multidisciplinary and the incorporation of technologies from
699 new fields, thus confirming the technological dynamism of this field. The evolution of 3D
700 DATA may evidence an increasing trend of incorporating new fields into its technical base,
701 but more data is needed to support this point. Finally, T&P stands out as the technology
702 front that is clearly below average on both interdisciplinarity and incorporation of new

703 fields, thus proving the highly specialized nature of this front. Note that SLA exhibits the
704 same spike we detected on IPCPAT.

705 This study also proposes a text mining approach for characterizing the technological change
706 (TERMVEC, NEWTERM). The results of calculating TERMVEC are presented in Fig 16:

707

708 **Fig 16. TERMVEC for each technology front.** This figure shows the evolution of the
709 TERMVEC indicator for each technology front. Data points above the bars indicate higher
710 than average Euclidean distance between term vectors

711 The analysis of distances between term vectors sends mixed signals, but we can observe
712 that MULTILAYER is showing certain changes in the concepts it deals with, this observation is
713 coherent with the trend shown by this front in the IPCNEW indicator. If we omit the overall
714 front spike in year 2016 then 3D DATA and T&P are also above the average in term distance.
715 Data points corresponding to year 2017 seem to confirm this behavior, but this result needs
716 to gain consistence in the light of more data. SLA is above average in this indicator, which is
717 coincident - once more - with the signals of technology change sent by previous indicators.

718 The analysis of NEWTERM (Fig 17) shows that the disparity of concepts unveiled in T&P
719 front is not due to the massive incorporation of new terms. This behavior is also coherent
720 with the “specialization” features of this front revealed in the previous analyses.

721

722 **Fig 17. NEWTERM for each technology front.** This figure shows the evolution of NEWTERM
723 indicator for each technology front. Data points above the bars indicate higher than average
724 presence of new and relevant terms.

725 The 3D DATA front may tell a different story, given that both text-mining indicators show
726 above the average technology change. PRINTMAT behavior is similar to that of 3D DATA in
727 NEWTERM evolution, but the erratic behavior of the former in TERMVEC indicator makes it
728 difficult to diagnose the changes this field is undergoing. Looking at SLA data, we again get a
729 red flashing light marking a substantial transformation taking place in this field.

730 **CONCLUSIONS**

731 This paper describes our approach for the detection of core technological solutions - which
732 we call “technology fronts” - underlying certain device or broad development (3D printing
733 has been the choice, as explained in the introduction) and the characterization of their
734 dynamics of change across time. After retrieving a dataset containing 3D printing patents
735 from database Patseer, we designed a text-mining procedure that allowed us to identify the

736 most relevant concepts these patents dealt with, according to the statements contained in
737 their claims. These terms were crossed with patents to build term-document matrices
738 corresponding to a set of time intervals that span from year 1985 to 2017. These matrices
739 were analyzed using a topic modeling technique, which has shed light on the technology
740 fronts being developed under the broad field of 3D printing. We found that some of these
741 fronts are in part coincident with the main taxonomies of typical devices in the 3d printing
742 industry, while others describe “hot points” where engineering efforts are put into practice
743 to improve critical aspect of the devices. In order to study the behavior of these technology
744 fronts, and considering the data-features of transversal developments, we opted for a
745 subsetting strategy based on the gamma values returned by the topic modeling solution for
746 each patent, so we could build sub-datasets containing the patents in which claims were
747 clearly focused on the topics identified by our approach. Metrics built on patent data were
748 used to characterize the rate of change of technology fronts, analyzing each of these on a
749 relative basis with respect to the values produced by the rest of the fronts.

750 The conclusions derived from our work could start by describing the features of the more
751 design related-electromechanical technology fronts underlying 3D printing, identified as
752 T&P (transmission and precision positioning technologies) and PRINTHEAD (design, control
753 and mechanics of printing head) fronts. These fronts show above average technological
754 relevance (FORPAT) and a low multidisciplinary profile, according to almost all indicators.
755 This could also be interpreted in terms of “high specialization” of these technology fronts.
756 Our conclusion is that fast, radical technological transformations are not taking place on
757 these fronts and data does not show evidence of any change in this trend. In spite of this,
758 many other developments may be dependent on the improvement of these technologies,
759 given the vital importance of these elements on the printing resolution capacity, and the
760 increasing demand for geometrically complex, micron-accurate printing of parts. The
761 “enabling” nature of these fronts would therefore explain their relevance.

762 A very different pattern is found in MULTILAYER. This is a technology front weak in
763 relevance that cites seemingly outdated sources (YEARBACK) but shows very clear signals of
764 undergoing multidisciplinary change, confirmed by both patent and text-mining analyses.
765 We believe that the signals of high dynamism detected on this front are probably related
766 with two of the future priorities for 3D printing described in Table 1, namely the use of
767 multiple printing materials on the object being printed, and the capacity of 3D printers to
768 produce finished products such as more-or-less complete printed circuit boards. According
769 to our data, technology change rate is high on this front and significant future innovations
770 can be expected to come from it. A milder but similar behavior is detected in 3D DATA, text-
771 mining indicators corroborate the trend shown by IPCNEW in the latter stages of this front.
772 In addition to this, the citation patterns also point at a field prone to change. 3D DATA also
773 has a direct impact on the software priorities cited at Table 1 [52].

774 The analysis of LASERBEAM technology front is conditioned by the scarcity of data available
775 due to its “novelty”: following our method this front is first detected in year 2014, precisely
776 the year in which many laser-sintering patents expired [10,52]. The considerable technical
777 challenges for processing metal and ceramic materials in 3D printing could in part explain
778 this novelty, but the development of this technology front is directly linked with future goals
779 of 3D printing technology such as multimaterial and finished product printing. Our analysis,
780 limited as it is due to the reduced amount of data available, simultaneously points at an
781 increase in relevance and a progressive modernization of the citations (as shown by FORPAT
782 and YEARBACK). This simultaneity indicates that in the future this front may present some of
783 the enabling characteristics that we attributed to PRINTHEAD and T&P in our conclusions. As
784 with these fronts, LASERBEAM shows signs of specialization, despite being more
785 multidisciplinary by nature.

786 Few conclusions can be extracted from the analysis of PRINTMAT, given the mixed signals
787 produced by our indicators. The highly multidisciplinary nature of this front led us to think
788 that a certain amount of technology changes may come from technical areas that fall
789 beyond 3D printing, therefore not captured by our query.

790 The SLA front shows very interesting behavior. This is a clearly defined technology front, the
791 interpretation of which did not raise doubts when it was present in an interval, however, its
792 presence is temporarily interrupted in interval 2006-12 and it finally disappears from our
793 model from year 2015 onwards. An analysis of the data shows relatively high values across
794 time in some variables related with technology change (TERMVEC, NEWTERM, IPCNEW),
795 combined with a noticeable spike in year 2015 in IPCPAT, NEWTERM AND IPCNEW. Experts
796 in the field (stereolithography) and our own research suggest that this technology may be
797 undergoing a pivotal change in the dominant technology from ultraviolet light to liquid
798 crystal display based devices, increased speed and reduced cost being some of the
799 advantages of this innovation [82–84]. Such radical changes can significantly alter the
800 vocabulary describing the technology, thus distorting the results of our text-mining based
801 approach, particularly when patents corresponding to the “old-school” technology get
802 mixed in with the patents of the new - noticeably different - technology. We may be at this
803 point regarding SLA technology.

804 We have presented a reproducible method for studying the underlying technologies that,
805 step by step, advance a device or broad technology (in this case, 3D printing) from early
806 implementations to “hot technologies”, and finally to widespread adoption. The technology
807 fronts and data revealed by our method have been convincing to experts and coincident
808 with many technology trends already pointed out in technical reports and scientific
809 literature. The limitations of our approach include those inherent to every text mining study:
810 the extraordinary amount of noise present in data and the influence that a moderate
811 number of observations can have on the results produced by the method, as shown in the
812 SLA case.

813 The authors would like to finish this section with the following sincere and perhaps slightly
814 disappointing sentence stated by Jaffe and Fogarty [76]: “Many of the important concepts in
815 the economics of technological change are fundamentally unobservable”. This sentence is
816 rigorously true, and we think that it could not be otherwise, given the extremely
817 multivariate nature of technological change, and the inherent immensurability - incidentally
818 admitting that there are certainly several “unknown unknowns” involved - of many of these
819 variables. We would like to instill the above stated conclusions with a humble admission of
820 this fact.

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